

AI Solar power harvesting

Moataz Weza Al-Moktashef

معتز وزة المكششف

CONTENTS

Abstract.....	2
Technologies.....	7
Problems.....	11
AI.....	18
REFERENCES	25

Abstract

Solar power is the process of turning solar energy directly into electricity using photovoltaics (PV), indirectly through concentrated solar power, or both.

The photovoltaic effect is used by photovoltaic cells to convert light into an electric current.

A vast region of sunlight is focused to a hot spot using concentrated solar power systems, which are frequently used to power a steam turbine.

The calculator powered by a single solar cell and rural dwellings powered by an off-grid rooftop PV system were the only large-scale applications powered by photovoltaics at first.

In the 1980s, the first commercial concentrated solar power facilities were created.

Since that time, grid-connected solar PV installations have increased roughly exponentially as the price of solar electricity has decreased.

Gigawatt-scale solar power plants and millions of installations have both been and are being constructed.

The most affordable source of electricity in history will be provided by solar photovoltaic technology by 2020.

In 2021, solar energy will produce 4% of the world's electricity, up from 1% in 2015, the year the Paris Climate Agreement was signed.

Utility-scale solar, along with onshore wind, has the lowest Levelized cost of power.

According to the International Energy Agency's "Net Zero by 2050" scenario, solar energy would account for nearly 20% of global energy consumption and rank as the top source of electricity by 2021.

In order to supplement or provide an alternative to fossil or nuclear energy sources, many industrialized countries have added significant solar power capacity to their grids. Meanwhile, an increasing number of less developed countries are turning to solar energy in order to lessen their reliance on pricey imported fuels.

Remote renewable energy sources can replace fossil fuel use thanks to long-distance transmission.

Technologies

One of two technologies is employed by solar power plants:

Photovoltaic cells

A solar cell, often known as a photovoltaic

cell (PV), is a machine that uses the photovoltaic effect to transform light into an electric current.

Charles Fritts created the first solar cell in the 1880s.

Ernst Werner von Siemens, a German manufacturer, was one among those who understood the significance of this finding.

Although the prototype selenium cells only converted 1% of incident light into energy, German engineer Bruno Lange created a photo cell in 1931 using silver selenide instead of copper oxide.

Researchers Gerald Pearson, Calvin Fuller,

and Daryl Chapin developed the silicon solar cell in 1954 as a result of Russell Ohl's work from the 1940s.

These early solar cells had efficiencies of 4.5–6% and were priced at US\$286/watt.

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Concentrated solar power

When sunlight is focused using lenses, mirrors, and tracking systems to create concentrated solar power, also known as "concentrated solar thermal," the heat produced is used to drive traditional steam-driven turbines to produce electricity.

There are several different concentrating devices; the parabolic trough, compact linear Fresnel reflector, Stirling dish, and solar power tower are some of the most well-known.

Light is focused and the sun is tracked using a variety of methods.

Each of these systems uses a working fluid that has been heated by concentrated sunlight and is then utilized to produce electricity or store energy.

Effective thermal storage enables up to 24-hour electricity production.

Problems

The fact that electricity can only be produced when the sun is shining is one of the main issues with solar energy

technology.

This means that the supply may be interrupted at night and on cloudy days.

If there were inexpensive means to store energy, the shortfall caused by this interruption would not be a concern because highly sunny periods can actually provide excess capacity.

Japan and other world leaders in solar energy technology are concentrating on creating adequate energy storage to address this issue as the demand for solar energy increases globally.

Compared to gas-fired power, concentrated solar power may consume significantly more water.

Solar energy, in contrast to systems based on fossil fuels, does not produce any harmful emissions when in use, however the manufacture of the panels does produce some pollution.

Solar energy has life-cycle greenhouse gas

emissions that are less than 50 grams (g) per kilowatt-hour (kWh).

While a coal-fired power station emits roughly 1000 g/kWh and a combined cycle gas-fired power plant around 500 g/kWh.

The site's solar insolation is the most important component because it has an inverse relationship with GHG emissions parameters for PV solar.

The transition to low carbon power in the manufacturing and delivery of solar devices will reduce greenhouse gas emissions, which are primarily caused by building for all energy sources.

According to estimates, solar electricity has a life-cycle surface power density of 6.63 W/m², which is two orders of magnitude lower than that of fossil fuels and nuclear power.

As a result, compared to sources with greater surface power densities and capacity factors, PV requires a substantially larger area of land surface to provide the same nominal amount of energy.

In the European Union, up to 2.8% of the entire landmass would be needed to achieve 80% PV by 2050, and up to 5% in nations like Japan and South Korea.

Residential opposition would probably be sparked by the occupation of such vast regions for PV farms, which would also likely result in deforestation, the destruction of flora, and the conversion of farmland.

Some solar technologies need the manufacturing of rare elements.

However, this is more of a challenge for PV

technology than CSP technology.

Additionally, the problem is less a lack of known reserves as it is the incapacity of current output to satisfy future demand, instead of being the goal of deliberate mining activities, many of the rare materials are byproducts of other processes.

AI

Machine learning algorithms are now frequently employed to enhance forecasting processes and stabilize the output of solar

energy.

Solar farms can use AI-powered inspection in a few different ways.

Using a drone or an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) is the most popular method.

UAVs offer solar farm operators a non-contact option to use airborne photography to do quality control on their solar panels.

Support vector machines (SVM), gradient boosting decision trees, and a number of others are among them.

In the past, owners of solar farms would

manually check solar panels for flaws with a team of personnel.

This procedure is cumbersome, costly, and not very precise.

Every owner of a solar farm is aware that maintenance visits are quite expensive and cannot realistically be carried out every day for the duration of solar deployment.

Solar farm operators are using AI-powered inspection to streamline the process and increase accuracy.

Algorithms that can automatically identify

solar panel flaws in photos are used in this.

Compared to manual inspection, this procedure is both quicker and more precise.

Operators of solar farms can also employ AI-powered inspection to spot damaged panels both before they are put in place on the solar farm and once, they are up and running.

Algorithms are dependable methods for addressing storage issues and enhancing power infrastructures.

In reality, a lot of sensors can be added to power grids to gather a lot of data.

This data can be usefully examined by artificial intelligence to give network operators more flexibility and control.

When it comes to renewable energy, which is susceptible to seasonal dynamics, energy storage technology is essential.

By building models using previously gathered data, artificial intelligence, and particularly machine learning, can assist in managing these flows and storing extra energy to prevent grid overloads.

Decentralized energy sources can transfer any extra electricity they generate to the grid with the use of AI software, and

utilities can route that electricity where it is required.

Similar to energy storage, which can keep extra energy when demand is low in homes, offices, cars, and other structures, AI can use that energy when generation is insufficient or impossible.

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